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Anowar's Handbook on Technical Textiles

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for textile engineers, civil engineers, medical professionals, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of technical textiles. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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Amir (or) Anwar
Technical Textile
01. Fibre Tech
02. Colour Tech
03. Jute and Fibre
04. Apparel & Fibre
05. Application of
Technical Textile

Tex-308: Technical Textiles

Rinat Khanum, 19/05/2023

***** what do you understand by technical textile?**

Ans: Frequently used term for textiles used for technical purpose. These are textiles, whose fibre substance and form, texture and weaving technique, impregnation, coating, rubberizing or composite construction render them independent technical products, are used in technical products or demonstrate technical or special industrial properties.

***** write down 2 about technical textile market?**

Ans:
In development countries: 50% of total textile products

Growth rate: World wide 3.8% for period 2000 to 2005

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5. Home tech: Technical component of furniture, house hold textiles and floor covering.

6. Indu tech: Filtration, conveying, cleaning and other industrial uses.

7. Med tech: Hygiene and medical

8. Mobil tech: Automobiles, shipping, rail ways and aerospace.

9. Oeko tech: Environmental protection

10. Pack tech: Packaging.

11. Pro tech: Personal and property protection.

12. Sport tech: Sport and leisure.

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*** Write down the application of Natural fibres?

Ans:

1. Cotton, Flax, jute, sisal = Heavy canvas-type products, ropes

2. Wool = Insulating, flame retardency
(a material or substance that is used to stop heat, electricity, or sound from getting into or out of something)

3. Silk = Surgical suture / surgical thread

*** Write the application of Synthetic fibre as Technical fibre.

1. Viacore rayon = Tyres, Drive belts, conveyors, automotive and industrial equipment. Due to good absorbency, wet laying techniques (non-woven application) use for hygiene products.

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2. Polyamide = High strength, abrasion resistance,
good elasticity, resistant to moisture

Products = climbing ropes, parachute fabrics, sail,
tyres

3. Polyester = Geo textiles, carpet, coverings

4. Polyolefins (mostly polypropylene but also polyethylene) = Low cost, easy processability, good abrasion and moisture resistance.

Products = Sacks, bags - packaging, carpet backing,
Furniture lining, ropes, netting, tape

*** Discuss about High performance fibres?

Ans: P-aramid = High strength and modulus

Products = Bullet proof vests, tyres,
friction materials, ropes, advanced
composites.

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2. Reinforcement of buildings and structures in earth quake zones.

(b) Gelam = Brittle, stiff, high modulus, Embedding in matrix form :-

Epoxy resins, polyester and other polymers as cement to make strength.

Use :

1. Cheap insulating, reinforcement and roofing material

2. Fire and heat resistant products

filtration, packaging, protective cloth, Rubber reinforcement.

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Discussion about Aramid filament yarn?

Ans:

Features of Aramid filament yarn:

Aramid has long chain synthetic polyamide where at least 85% of the amide linkages are attached directly to two aromatic rings.

Aramid fibre has high tenacity, high resistance to stretch, chemicals and high temperature.

Aramid easy to weaving, knitting or braiding.

Types:

Nomex and kevlar are 2 well known trade names of aramid fibre owned by Du-pont.

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1. ~~Kevlar aramid~~ is well known for its relatively light weight and damage resistance. ~~Kevlar can~~

uses: Kevlar used in composite (boat, air craft)

2. Nomex aramid on the other hand is heat resistance used in making fire fighting apparel.

*** Discuss about Glass filament yarn? ***

Ans:

Features:

*** In combustible (fire resistance)

Yarn/fibre, high tenacity, used

for fire retardant application.

high insulation, low cost, used

for reinforcement for composites.

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It is 4-5 times rigid than wool.
~~It is~~ Easy to break in textile processing.

It is important to apply suitable size to glass yarn to minimise the inter-fibre friction and to hold the individual fibres together in strand.

Distinguished starch, gum, gelatine, poly-vinyl alcohol, hydro-generated vegetable oils and non ionic detergents are commonly used as size.

Types:

E-glass = High resistance to attack by moisture, high electric and heat resistant.

Uses: To make glass-reinforced plastics in the form of woven fabric.

C-glass = chemical resistance to both acid and alkali

Uses: To make chemical filtration.

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S-glass = High strength glass fibre.

Uses: Used in composite manufacturing.

Precaution: When handling glass fibres, protective clothing and a mask should be worn to prevent skin irritation and inhalation of glass fibres.

(কুরাকাফা)
(স্বাসভক্ষিত)

*** Discuss about carbon filament yarn? ***

Ans:

Made from pre-cursor fibres such as PAN, rayon and acrylic.

When converting acrylic fibre to carbon, a 3 stage heating process is used.

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How to control... $H_2 + F_2 \rightarrow 2HF$
 $H_2 \rightarrow H^+ + 2e^-$
 $F_2 + 2e^- \rightarrow 2F^-$
oxidising

loss of electron

a. Oxidation: The initial stage in oxidation, stabilization, heats the acrylic fibre at 200-300°C, under oxidising condition

b. Carbonisation stage: The oxidised fibre is heated in an inert atmosphere to temperatures around 1000°C. Consequently, H and N atoms are expelled from the oxidised fibre, leaving the carbon atoms in the form of the hexagonal rings that are arranged in oriented fibrils.

(A material with unstable Carbon)

c. Graphitisation: Carbonised filaments heated up to 3000°C, again in an inert atmosphere, graphitisation increases the orderly arrangement of the carbon atoms, which are organised into crystalline structure of layers. These layers are well oriented in the direction of fibre axis.

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Precaution: when handling carbon fibres, protective clothing and a mask should be worn to prevent skin irritation and inhalation of glass carbon fibres.

*** What is the amount of plain weave of Technical fabrics

Ans: 90%

*** What is the amount of special fabric of Technical fabrics.

Ans: 10%

*** Describe about leno fabrics?

Ans: Leno fabrics are a type of technical fabric characterized by their unique weaving pattern, which creates a series of loops or 'lenos' in the fabric structure. This structure provides enhanced strength and stability, making them suitable for applications requiring high performance and durability. Leno fabrics are commonly used in technical textiles, such as geotextiles, reinforcement materials, and industrial fabrics.

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Fig:01 Same length of crossing and standard end

Fig:02 Different length of crossing and standard end

Leno weave/cross weave: in a weave in which two warp yarns are twisted around the weft yarn to provide strength. standard warp yarn is paired with a skeleton or dope yarn.

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Leno fabric consists of standard and
crossing ends only or pairs or multiples
of such threads may be introduced
according to pattern to obtain the
required design.

Fig. 02: Two or more weft threads
may be introduced into one shed and
areas of fabric may be woven in the
weft direction between picks where
warp ends are crossed over to give
the Leno effect.

This type of fabric used for
filtration, in selvedge standard and
crossing ends frequently come from
separate warp beams.

* Warp threads cross over each other
with the weft passing between them, they lock the
weft into position and prevent weft movement.

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Why leno ends are used in woven fabric
Leno ends are used to prevent the warp threads
from slipping out of the body of fabric. For
selvedge 1 to 4 pairs of thread come from cones
in a small separate reel.

*** Discuss about Tri-axial weavers? ***

Ans: Where two sets of warp yarn are generally
inserted at 60° to the weft and tetra-axial fabric
where four sets of yarns are inclined at 45°
to each other. Tri-axial fabrics are defined as
cloth where three sets of threads form an equi-
lateral triangle. Two sets of warp yarn are
interlaced at 60° with each other and with the
weft.

Fig: Tri-axial fabric

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West yarn is inserted at right angle (90°) to selvedge. To basic tri-axial fabric is fairly open with a diamond-shaped centre. The tear and bursting resistance is superior.

Product: sail cloth, tyre fabric, balloon fabrics.

What do you understand by Tetra-axial fabric?

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*** Discuss about shedding in multiphase weaving m/c.

Ans: In all multiphase weaving m/c's several phases of the working cycle take place at any instant. So that several picks are being inserted simultaneously.

Different parts of warp shed are different parts of weaving cycle.

Wave shed principle (west way multiphase)

Several sheds are formed simultaneously

Multiphase parallel shed principle

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To reduce irregularities of
for ~~weave~~ shed machines different
parts of the warp sheet are in different
parts of the weaving cycle at any one
moment. This makes it possible for a
series of shuttles or weft carriers to
move along in successive sheds in the
same plane.

For parallel shed m/c several sheds are
formed simultaneously with each shed
extending across the full width of the
warp and with the shed moving in the
warp direction.

Multiphase Parallel shed principle

Discuss about circular weaving m/c

Circular knitting m/c, circular garment Prodⁿ

Ans: Weaving m/c's in which shuttles

travels a circular path through the weave
shed are generally referred to as circular
weaving m/c.

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perfect blend of ~~combined~~ **combined shed/forcing reed**
injection channel

Best cap reed

Rotating Drum

Fig. Sulzer Textile multiphase parallel shed M8300

Shuttle → 300 picks/min
 Air Jet → 1500 PPM
 Water Jet → 1000 PPM
 Rapiert loom → 1050 PPM

Shuttle
 Dividing Beams

Air jet type, which is operating at up to 5000 m/min needs no healds, has a rotating drum.

End uses: Hosiery, sacks, clothing, fabric horse (tulle horse) (related to knitting) → stocking/socks.

Horse → Hosiery → Hosiery

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*** Write down the difference between
Rachel m/c and Ttricot m/c

Ans: Rachel m/c

Ttricot m/c

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1. Compound and latch needle used | 1. Bearded and compound needle used. |
| 2. Have trick plate | 2. Have sinker bar. |
| 3. Fabric taken up parallel to needle stems. | 3. Fabric taken up right angle to needles. |
| 4. Have coverlet gauge | 4. Finer gauge than Rachel m/c. |
| 5. Warp beam on top of m/c | 5. Warp beam of the back of m/c. |
| 6. Versatile (staple yarn, split, films used) | 6. Only continuous filament yarn used. |

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Q. Write down the specifications for t-shirt

Ans:
Type of needle : Compound, bearded.

Needle gauge : 18-40 needle per inch
(E18-E40)

Needle width : 213-533 cm (84-210 inches)

Needle speed : 2000 to 3500 courses per minute.

Number of needle bars : one or two

Number of guide bars : 2 to 8

Products : shirts, outer wear, leisure wear, sports wear, car seat covers, upholstery, bed linen, towelling etc.

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Composites

Resin: Resin is any class of solid, semi-solid or

liquid organic material, generally the product of natural or synthetic origin with a high molecular weight and with no melting point. The resin are highly branched polymers that cure to solids, usually soluble in solvent until cured. Their degree of hardness when cured depends on the extent of cross-linking i.e urea melamine.

Epoxy: Epoxy resins are a group of cross-linking polymers and are sometimes known as the oxirane group.

Laminates: Laminates can be defined as combination of liquid resins with reinforcing materials that are bonded together by application of heat and pressure, forming an infusible matrix. carbon, glass etc.

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Process about the processes of resin

Compositing to have good properties. The resin is poured into the reinforcement material and the combined resin-reinforcement sheet is then placed in a horizontal trough. At first resin is dissolved in a solvent to achieve optimum wetting or saturation of resin into the reinforcement. The sheets come out of the trough and are sheeted to size and stacked (arranged).

Ans:
The liquid resin is poured into the reinforcement material and the combined resin-reinforcement sheet is then placed in a horizontal trough. At first resin is dissolved in a solvent to achieve optimum wetting or saturation of resin into the reinforcement. The sheets come out of the trough and are sheeted to size and stacked (arranged).

Trough:
Temp: 122 to 204°C
Pressure: 200 to 3000 lb/in²
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Write down the example of reinforcement materials :

Fiberglass, Graphite/Carbon, Aramid, Boron

Load elongation curves :

Fig: Reinforced plastic

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*** Write down the examples of composites

Application/ear examples	Used material
Tanks, piping	Glass, vinyl esters, chloroendic resins
Industrial rolls for paper and films	Carbon/graphite, epoxy resins
CNG tanks	Carbon, graphite, Fibers, glass, epoxy resins.

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Write down the advantages and disadvantages of composites?

Advantages:

1. Weight reduction
2. High strength
3. Longer life time
4. Lower manufacturing cost

Dis-advantages:

1. Cost of raw material high
2. Difficult to attach

Write down the used fibre for composites?

Ans:

1. Carbon/ Graphite
2. Glass
3. Organic - Aramid
- Polyethylene
- PBO (Poly (p-phenylene-2,6-benzo biquinoxalene))

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*** Woven fabrics attractive compared to non-

woven counter parts — Explain it

Ans:

1. Woven fabric have very good dt capability, allowing complex shapes to be formed with no gaps.
2. Manufacturing costs are reduced since a single bi-axial fabric replaces two nonwoven plies
3. Woven fabric composites show an increased tenintance to impact damage compared to nonwoven composites.

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Fibres are used : Carbon, glass, Aramid

Stitching thread : Polyester rayon.

In its more sophisticated form,
chain or tricot stitches are used to produce

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a fabric which consists of warp (0°), weft (90°)
and bias ($\pm \theta$) yarn held together by warp-
knitted stitches, which usually consist of light
polyester yarn. The resulting fabric is called
a non-stump (NEF) or multiaxial warp-knit (MxK)
fabric.

*** Discuss about Nonwoven fabric? ***

Ans: A nonwoven is a textile structure produced
by the bonding or interlocking of fibres, or both,
accomplished by mechanical, chemical, thermal or
solvent means and combinations thereof.

*** Write down the # types of laying of nonwoven fabric. ***

Ans: There are two types of laying.

1. Parallel Laying : Laying several card webs
over each other.

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Cross laying: The card web is traversed back wards and forwards across the main conveyor. The result is in a zig-zag form.

*** Write down the types of bonding of non-woven fabric?

aqueous → containing water

Ans:

1. Chemical bonding: Using adhesive binders applied by aqueous impregnation for processing, coating, printing or water-based spraying methods.

Fig: Dry laid / chemical bonded non woven

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Thermoplastic: denoting substances that become plastic on heating and harden on cooling and are able to repeat these processes. ^{→ Soften}

2. Thermal bonding: Makes use of the thermoplastic nature of the web. Bonding is achieved using a calendaring process, by controlled hot air, infra-red heaters. ^{(800 nm - μ m) wave length.}

Bi-component fibres: (Being a fibre made of two polymer)

Fig. 1 Thermal bonding mechanism

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3. Needle Punching / Mechanical bonding: Needles

are inserted into the web which force some of the fibres down-ward causing them to be entangled with fibres in lower layers of the web. Further entanglement occurs on the upward movement of the needles.

Fig: - Needle punched nonwovens

4. Hydro-entanglement: By the use of high pressure jets of water and bonds the web together and a wide range of novel effects can be obtained (water pressure 400 bar).

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Fig: Hydro-entanglement bonded

Write down the used fibre in non woven?

Ans:

1. Viscose
2. Polyester
3. Polyamide
4. Polypropylene
5. Flax
6. Cotton

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*** Discuss about non wovens in the cat ?

Ans:

1. Filters,
2. Carpeting.
3. Covering for moulded seats.
4. Covering for seat belt.
5. Covering for inside roof lining.
6. Door trim pads.

*** Discuss about non wovens in medical textile ?

Ans: The major requirements for biomedical polymers.

1. Strength
2. Elasticity
3. Durability
4. Non allergic response
5. Nontoxic

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Categories of medical textiles:

1. Non-implantable materials
2. Implantable materials (To insert or graft (a tissue, organ) into the body)
3. Extra corporeal devices
4. Health care and hygiene products.

Non-implantable materials:

Fibre type	Fabric structure	Application
1. Cotton, viscose, Lyocell	Non woven	of Abdominal band pad
2. Cotton, viscose, Lyocell, polyamide, elastomeric fibre	Woven, nonwoven, knitted	Simple non-elastic and elastic bandages.
3. Cotton, viscose, Lyocell, elastomeric fibre	Woven, knitted	Compression bandages.
4. Cotton, viscose, Lyocell, Polyester, Polypropylene, Poly urethane foam	Woven, Non-woven	Orthopedic bandage.
5. Lyocell, alginate, fibre, chitosan	Non-woven knitted	Gauge-Dressing

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2. Extra-corporeal devices → Bodily/physical

Product application	Fibre type	Function
Artificial Kidney	Hollow, viscose, hollow, Polyester	Remove waste products from Patients blood
Artificial Liver	Hollow, viscose	Separate and dispose patients plasma and supply fresh plasma (colorless fluid part of blood)
Mechanical Lung	Hollow, poly propylene, hollow, silicone, silicone membrane	Remove carbon dioxide from Patients blood and supply fresh blood

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3. Implantable materials:

Product application	Fibre type	Manufacture system
<u>Sutures:</u> (a) Biodegradable	Collagen, Polyketide, Polyglycolide	Mono filament, Braided
(b) Non-biodegradable	Polyamide, Polyester, PTFE, Polypropylene	Mono filament, Braided

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Orthopedic implants :

Product application	Fibre type	Manufacturing system
Artificial joints / bones	Silicone, Polyacetal, Polyethylene	

Cardiovascular implants :

Vascular grafts	Polyester, PTFE	Knitted, woven
Heart valves	Polyester	Woven, knitted

Healthcare / Hygiene products :

Surgical clothing :

Gowns	cotton, polyester, Polypropylene	Woven & non-woven
Cap	Viacore	Nonwoven
Masks	Viacore, polyester, glass	Nonwoven

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<u>Surgical covers:</u>		
Drapes (To be loosely covered with the cloth)	Polyester	Non woven
	Polyethylene	Woven
<u>Bedding:</u>		
Blankets	cotton, polyester	Woven, Knitted
Sheets	cotton	Woven
Pillow cases	cotton	Woven
<u>clothing:</u>		
Uniforms	cotton, polyester	Woven
Protective clothing	Polyester, Propylene	Non woven

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<u>Surgical honeyery</u>	Polyamide, Polyester, cotton, elastomeric rayon	Knitted
Cloths	Viscose	Nonwoven

Discern about medical fibres

Ans: Biodegradable fibres: Biodegradable fibres are those which are absorbed by the body within 2-3 months after implantation i.e cotton, viscose, rayon, polyamide, polyurethane, collagen and alginate fibres.

Nonbiodegradable fibres: fibres that are slowly absorbed within the body and take more than 6 months to degrade are considered nonbiodegradable fibres i.e polyester, polypropylene, PTFE, (teflon) and carbon.

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Collagen fibres : collagen fibres used as sutures, etc as strong as silk and are biodegradable.

chitin nonwoven fibres : chitin nonwoven fibres used as artificial skin adhere to the body stimulating new skin formation which accelerates the healing rate and reduce pain.

*** Discuss about Bandages of textile?

Ans:

Bandages : They can be woven, knitted or nonwoven and either elastic or non-elastic. Knitted bandages can be produced in tubular form in varying diameters.

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Compression bandages : Compression bandages

are used for the treatment and prevention of deep vein thrombosis (জন্মকৃত) • leg ulceration and varicose veins (বর্জিত) and are designed to exert a required amount of compression on the leg when applied at a constant tension.

Orthopaedic cushion bandages :

Orthopaedic cushion bandages are used under plaster casts and compression bandages to provide padding and prevent discomfort. Non-woven orthopaedic cushion bandages may be produced from either polyurethane foams • polyester or polypropylene fibres and certain blends of natural or other synthetic fibres. Nonwoven bandages are lightly needle punched to maintain bulk and soft.

A space directly under the foot

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*** Discuss about extra corporeal devices of medical textiles

Ans:

Artificial Kidney: The function of the artificial kidney is achieved by circulating the blood through a membrane, which may be either a flat sheet or a bundle of hollow regenerated cellulose fibres in the form of cellophane that retain the unwanted waste materials. Multilayered filters composed of numerous layers of needle punched fabrics are designed rapidly and efficiently to remove the waste materials.

*** Discuss about implantable materials

Ans: Four key factors will determine how the body reacts to the implant:

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1. The most important factor in porosity (the blank space between warp and weft) which determines the rate at which human tissue will grow and encapsulate the implant.
2. Small circular fibres are better encapsulated (covered) with human tissue than larger fibres with irregular cross-sections.
3. Toxic substances must not be released by the fibre polymer, and fibres should be free from surface contaminants such as lubricants and sizing agents.
4. The properties of the polymer will influence the success of the implantation in terms of its biodegradability.

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Q. Discuss about sutures of implantable materials?

Ans:

Sutures for wound closure are either monofilament or multifilament threads that are categorized as either biodegradable or non-biodegradable. Biodegradable sutures are used mainly for internal wound closures and nonbiodegradable sutures are used to close exposed exposed wounds and are removed when the wound is sufficiently healed.

Q. Discuss about soft-tissue implants?

Ans:

- (i) Tendon
- (ii) Ligament
- (iii) Cartilage

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(i) Tendon: Artificial tendon are woven or braided porous meshes.

(ii) Ligament: Textile materials used to replace damage knee ligaments. Braided composite materials containing carbon and polyester filament have also been found to be particularly suitable for knee ligament replacement.

(iii) Cartilage: Low density polyethylene is used to replace facial, nose, ear and throat cartilage. Carbon fibre reinforced composite structures are used to resurface the defective areas of articular cartilage.

relating to a joint

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~~Q~~ Discuss about Orthopaedic implants?

Ans: To replace bones and joints -
fibre-reinforced composite materials
may be designed with the required high
structural strength and biocompatibility
properties needed for these applications
and now replacing metal implants for
artificial joints and bones.

~~Q~~ Discuss about cardiovascular implants?

Ans: Vascular grafts are used in
surgery to replace damaged thick arteries
(Artery)
or veins (Vein) 6mm, 8mm, or 1mm in
diameter. Produced from polyester, PTFE
(Teflon) with either woven or knitted
structures. Straight or branched grafts
are possible by using either water and
weft knitting technology.

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*** Discuss about Health care/Hygiene products
of implantable material.

Ans: Textile material used in the operating theatre include surgeon's gown, caps, masks, patient drapes and cover cloths of various sizes.

Surgical gown should act as a barrier to prevent the release of pollutant particles into the air. Disposable nonwoven surgical gown have been adopted to prevent contamination to the patient and are often composite materials comprising nonwoven and polyethylene films for examples.

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Geo Textile

✓ Write short notes of Geo textiles

Ans: Geo textiles basically fall into five categories - woven, heat bonded non-woven, needle punched nonwoven, knitted and by fibre/soil mixing.

Woven fabrics : Lighter weight form an soil separator, filters and erosion control textiles. Heavy weights, they are used for soil reinforcement in steep embankments and vertical soil walls.
↓ almost Percepsal reader

Needle punched Nonwoven : Thickness 10 mm, weights greater than 20 gm⁻². Water knitting machines can produce fine filter fabrics, medium meshes and large diameter soil reinforcing grids.
(mesh)

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*** Write down the main geotextile fibre-forming polymers?

Ans:

- (1) Polymer is used when high strengths are required.
- (2) Polypropylene and polyethylene for being the most chemically resistant.
- (3) Polyamide: Resistance to abrasion.
- (4) Polyvinylidene chloride fibre is used in Japan and USA.

*** Write down the essential properties of geotextiles:

- Ans:
- (i) Filtration
 - (ii) Chemical resistance
 - (iii) Mechanical properties.

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Discuss about damage, Remedies and

Precaution of Geo textiles?

Ans:

Damage in Geotextile: Geotextile Damage can be caused on the construction period or in during use (e.g. punching through geotextiles by overlying angular stone)

Remedies: A thick nonwoven fabric may be joined to woven fabric, the woven textile performs the tensile work whilst the nonwoven acts as a damage protective cushion

Precaution: when laying textiles on soft ground for supporting embankments, parallel sheets of textile have to be sewn together so that they do not separate under load.

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✓ Write down some different drainage and filtration applications for geotextiles in civil Engineering.

①

②

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Embankment support

Road way separation

~~***~~ Discern about Essential properties
✓ of Geo-textiles

Ans:

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Lining → অর্ধস্রাবীত আবরণ

Ditch → নদীকা Beneath = under

1. Filtration properties: They are use in the lining of ditches, beneath roads, in waste disposal facilities, for building basement drainage and in many other ways. In just about all other applications including drains, access roads, river defences, marine defences, embankment support and concrete pouring, the geotextile will play a primary or secondary filtering function.

Disposal = অপসারণ

Some different drainage and filtration applications for geotextiles in civil Engineering:

[Previous topics]

earthwork = মাটি সরানো

It is important in civil Engineering earthwork that water should flow freely through the geotextile. The filtration effect is achieved by placing the textile against the soil in close contact.

Emulsion → মিশ্রিত

Permittivity → প্রদ্রব্য

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Geotextile

Filter জরুরি।
 In the soil, water travels through the soil and escapes through the geotextile.

Woven fabric acts as a shield protecting the nonwoven from the liquid and emulating a soil surface, thus permitting the nonwoven to function more effectively as a filter.

Emulation → প্রতিস্থাপিত
 Permitting → অনুমতি

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২. Chemical deterioration % The chemical mechanism involved in fibre degradation etc. complex, there are four main agents of deterioration: organic, inorganic, light exposure and time change within the textile fibres (অত্যাধিক কয়)

[microfauna → those invisible by naked eye]

Organic agents attack by micro and macro-fauna. Microorganisms may damage the textiles by living on or within the fibres and producing detrimental by products. (ক্ষয়কর)

Inorganic attack is generally restricted to extreme pH environments under most practical conditions, geotextile polymers are effectively inert. There are particular instances, such as: polyester being attacked by pH levels greater than 11.

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Geotextile can fail in their filtration
function by virtue of organisms multi-
plying and blocking the pores or by
chemical precipitation from saturated
mineral water blocking the pores (pore).

Ultraviolet light will deteriorate geo-
textile fibres if exposed for significant
periods of time.

But laboratory testing has shown
that fibres will deteriorate on their own
with time, even if stored under
dry dark cool conditions in a laboratory.
Therefore, time itself is a damaging
agent.

3. Mechanical properties :

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Ques Discuss about Natural fibre geotextile?

Ans:

Natural fibre geotextiles are only required to function for a limited time period whereas suitable synthetic materials often have a long life.

Natural fibre products of vegetable origin will be much more environmentally friendly than their synthetic equivalents and the fibres themselves are a renewable resource and biodegradable.

All natural fibres will biodegrade in the long term as a result of the action of micro-organisms. In certain situations this biodegradation may be advantageous.

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Example :

1. Best fibres : Flax, hemp, jute.

2. Leaf fibres : Abaca and sisal

3. Seed and fruit fibres : silk, cotton

*** Write down the applications for natural geotextiles?

Ans:

1. Soil reinforcement : Soil is comparatively strong in compression, but weak in tension. Therefore, if a tensile inclusion (geotextile) is added to the soil and forms intimate contact with it, a composite material can be formed.

(a) Long-term embankments : Hillside, stabilisation, embankment and flood bank strengthening and construction over soft ground etc.

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Bottom Mounting: 1. Water level
(b) Short-term embankments:

Temporary roads/structures

(2) Drainage: Fluid transmission

(3) Filtration: A geotextile acts as a filter by permitting the flow of liquid and gases, but preventing the passage of soil particles which can cause settlement due to loss of ground.

(4) Separation: A geotextile acts as a separator by preventing the inter-mixing of coarse and fine soil materials whilst allowing the free flow of water across the geotextile. When a geotextile is placed between the subsoil and granular sub-base of an unpaved road, it prevents the aggregate from being punched down into

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the soil during initial compaction and subsequently from the dynamic loading of vehicle axles

5. Erosion control: The usage differs from the other applications of geotextiles in that they are laid on the surface and not buried in the soil.

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*** Discuss about Mobil tech/ Transport textiles

Ans:

1. Cars, lorries, buses, trains, ships, aerospace.
2. Carpeting, seating, tyre, belt, hose reinforcement, safety belts, air bags, composite reinforcement, automotive bodies, civil and military aircraft bodies, wings, engine components, piping, tanks.
3. Carbon, glass, polyester can be used.

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Discuss about home textiles

Ans:

1. Hollow fibres with excellent insulating properties are widely used in bedding and sleeping bags.

2. Carpets, furniture backing, etc. are another examples.

3. Household cleaning application.

Discuss about cloth Tech textile

Ans:

Sewing threads, interlinings, insulation products (to provide an additional degree of control and resistance to sudden extremes of temperature, be they hot or cold).

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1 hour 840 9
Discern about Build tech textile/ construction

textile ?

Ans:

1. Building, both permanent and temporary, dams, bridges, tunnels, roads (সাঁও)
2. Temporary: Tents, marquees, awnings (আব্রিসমান)
3. Semi-permanent: sports, stadia, exhibition centre, modern building
4. Non-woven glass and polyester = roofing
5. Special non-woven = Prevent moisture condensation and dripping (সেঁকো সোঁকো পড়া)
6. Double wall spacer fabrics = Sound and thermal insulation

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7. G/Glass reinforced = wall panels, septic tank
and sanitary fittings.

8. G/Glass, polypropylene, acrylic = To prevent
cracking of concrete, plaster and
other building material.

9. G/Glass = Bridge construction

10. Carbon = Reinforcement for earth
quake-prone buildings.

11. Netting, lifting-tensioning ropes

12. Figure of Textile made roof/
construction is given below:

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*** Discern about Packing and containment of textile? ***

Ans:

Sacks, Bags

Traditionally from cotton, flax, jute, polypropylene.

*** Lighter weight nonwoven and knitted structures: Wrapping, protection.

*** Tea and coffee bags: Wet-laid nonwoven

*** Meats, vegetables, fruits bags = Nonwoven

*** Fruit and vegetable bags = Knitted net

Packaging

*** Envelope = Light weight spun bonded nonwoven.

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Q. Discuss about protective and safety clothing and Textiles?

Ans: Protection against cuts, abrasion, ballistic, stab wounds, explosions, fire, extreme heat, hazardous dust-particles, nuclear, biological and chemical hazards, high voltages, static electricity, foul weather, extreme cold.

Requirements: Garments are well designed and comfortable to wear.

Fibres: Aramid, Kevlar etc.

[Foul weather: unpleasant, windy weather.]

A stab wound is a specific form of penetrating trauma to the skin that results from a knife or a similar pointed object that "deeper than its wide)

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